

THE MAIN CAUSES OF FETOPLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528427>

Jurayeva Dildora Mukhitdinovna

"Gulnigor shifo med" LLC,

Termez district, Surkhandarya region

Obstetrician-gynecologist of "Oktash" clinic

Head of the maternity department

Fetoplacental insufficiency (FPI) is a complex of symptoms caused by various disorders of the placenta and fetus due to various diseases and obstetric complications. This symptom complex is very relevant today, because there is no clear cause, and the causes found are relative. Fetoplastic insufficiency is very common in obstetric practice. According to statistics, this pathology is rare in 50-70% of cases, gestosis develops - 30-33%, more than 60% in pregnant women with maternal infections-extragenital diseases (treatment, surgery, etc.) - 20-40 %.

FPI can develop under the influence of various causes. Disorders of the formation and function of the placenta can be diseases of the cardiovascular system of the pregnant woman (heart defects, circulatory failure, arterial hypertension and hypotension), kidney, liver, lung, blood pathology, chronic infection. Diseases of the neuroendocrine system (diabetes, hypo- and hyperfunction of the thyroid gland, pathology of the hypothalamus and adrenal glands) and a number of other pathological conditions. FPI in anemia is associated with decreased iron levels in both the mother's blood and the placenta itself, leading to inhibition of the activity of respiratory enzymes and the transport of iron to the fetus. In diabetes, metabolism is disrupted, hormonal disorders and changes in immune status are detected. Sclerotic disease of the blood vessels leads to a decrease in arterial blood flow to the placenta. FPI plays an important role in the development of various infectious diseases, especially those that occur in acute form or are aggravated during pregnancy. The placenta can be affected by bacteria, viruses, protozoa and other infectious agents.

Equally important uterine pathology in the formation of FPI: endometriosis, myometrial hypoplasia, uterine malformation (saddle-shaped, bifurcated). Uterine fibroids should be considered as a risk factor for FPI. However, the risk of FPI is different in pregnant women with uterine fibroids. The high-risk group includes primiparas aged 35 years and older, which are mainly located in the intramuscular location of large fibroid nodules, especially if the placenta is located in the tumor area. The group at low risk for FPI is young women under the age of 30 who do not have severe extragenital diseases, small myomatous nodules, mainly subperitoneal located at the base of the uterus and body.

Preeclampsia is often the leading complication of pregnancy associated with FPI. Preeclampsia not only disrupts the satellite's blood circulation, the whole body's water-salt balance, the content of micro and macronutrients. Abortion should be considered as both a

cause and a consequence of FPI. Due to the different etiology of FPI with the threat of abortion, the pathogenesis of this complication has different options and the prognosis for the fetus depends on the level of development of protective and adaptive reactions. With low placement or placenta previa, vascularization of the subplacental zone is reduced. The thin wall of the lower segment of the uterus does not provide adequate vascularization of the placental bed and the necessary conditions for its normal functioning.

Clinical practice and research results suggest a multifactorial nature of FPI. In this regard, it is almost impossible to distinguish any factor in the development of this complication. The frequency of occurrence of this disease is also different. Also, pathological conditions do not equally affect the development of FPI. Often, several etiological factors are involved in the development of this pathology, one of which may be leading. Pathological changes associated with FPI lead to decreased uteroplacental and fetoplacental blood flow; decreased arterial blood supply to the placenta and fetus; in the fetoplacental complex is limited gas exchange and metabolism.

The clinical signs listed in the early stages of FPI development may be mild or absent. In this regard, laboratory and instrumental dynamic monitoring methods of fetoplacental complex status in the high-risk group are important for the development of FPI.

The ultrasound examination determines the size of the fetus (head, trunk, and limb sizes) and compares it with the normative parameters specific to the expected gestation period. The basis of ultrasound diagnosis to determine whether the size of the fetus corresponds to the expected gestational age and to determine the intrauterine growth retardation of the fetus is to compare fetometric parameters with normative data. A prerequisite is the assessment of the anatomical structures of the fetus to detect abnormalities in its development. Sonographic examination involves the placenta. It determines the localization of the placenta, the thickness of the placenta, the distance from the inner part of the placenta, the degree of maturity of the placenta to the gestational age, the location of pathological appendages in the placental structure. With respect to myomatous nodes of the placenta or scar in the uterus. The study assesses the volume of amniotic fluid, the structure of the umbilical cord and the location of the umbilical cord.

Thus, placental insufficiency develops in complex pregnancies, which requires therapeutic and prophylactic measures aimed at reducing obstetric pathology. The problem of treating placental insufficiency has not yet been fully resolved, so the correction of the disorders should start better before pregnancy, which can reduce complications of pregnancy, fetus and newborn. Unfortunately, although the diagnosis of FPI is not difficult, it is not possible for our women to detect the disease early, because our women do not consult a doctor before or after pregnancy.

REFERENCES:

1. Fedorova M. V. Placental insufficiency // Obstetrics and gynecology. 1997. No. 6. P. 40–43.
2. Serov VN Diagnosis and treatment of placental insufficiency // BC. 2008, pp. 35–40.
3. Kuzmin V. N., Adamyan L. V., Muzykantova V. S. Placental insufficiency in viral infections // M.: 2005. P. 103.
4. Shapovalenko S.A. Comprehensive diagnosis and treatment of placental insufficiency in pregnant women at different stages of pregnancy. Association of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. 2001. No. 2. S. 437-son.
5. Salafiya C. M. Placenta pathology and fetal growth restriction // Clin.Obstet.Gynecol. 2007. 40. 7409 RU.MPG.11.02.11.
6. Jo`rayeva Dildora Mukhitdinovna. (2022). PREEKLAMSIYANING HOMILAGA TA'SIRI. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 2(4), 4–7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473270>
7. Juraeva Dildora Mukhitdinovna. (2022). Nay Peritoneal Type of Female Infertility (Mkb-10 / N 97.1). Texas Journal of Medical Science, 7, 77–78. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjms/article/view/1311>
8. Juraeva Dildora Mukhitdinovna. (2022). Changes in the Women's Body During the Climate Period. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 7, 90–91. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjms/article/view/1314>
9. Juraeva Dildora Mukhitdinovna. (2022, April 25). THE COURSE OF FETOPLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY, SEVERITY AND SPECIFICITY OF TREATMENT. International scientific-online conference: "INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM", USA Washington. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6481791>